

RECURSIVE FORMULA FOR NUMBER OF COWS IN MILK PRODUCTION*

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SUMMARY: We study the dependence of maximum number of cows K_n after n years, involved in milk production, on following parameters: an initial number of pregnant heifers K , average percentage of successful calving, calving of female calves and twin calving, marked as p_1 , p_2 and p_3 , respectively. We have established a recursive formula for maximum number of cows K_n . If $n=4$, then $K_4=(1+p) \cdot (1+3p) \cdot K$, where p stands for average percentage increase in number of cows after two years; $\mathbf{p}$ is 88% of p , where $\mathbf{p}$ stands for average annual percentage increase in number of female calves. It has been performed an analysis for percentage increase in number of cows K_n in milk productions, if the percentage of calving is between 80% and 90%, for $n=2,3,4,5,6$. Proposed formulae can be used for numerous additional financial analyses in milk production.

Key words: closed household, mathematical model, economical analysis, milk production, pregnant heifers

INTRODUCTION

In introductory motivational part of the textbook Economy and Financial Mathematics (Matić-Kekić, 2006a), there is a simplified problem we would like to engage in milk production: How many heifers should be obtained per livestock unit so that after the expiry of 8 years we can acquire 500 cows, if its known that 95 % of cows calve every year and that 50% of that number make female calves? The book does not contain the solution of this problem, so the task was given (for the last 5 years) to the students (about 600 – 700 students) of the Faculty of Agriculture, Novi Sad for individual work with explanatory note that cows from the flock are already pregnant and that in the year of their research we can expect the first offspring. After all, three students, managed to get the right solution applying foot-by-foot calculation.

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MATERIAL AND METHODS

In this paper, we have applied one mathematical method of modeling - recursive formula (Acketa and Matić-Kekić, 2000) with initial data and one statistic method (nonlinear regression), which has been applied in (Matić-Kekić, 2006; Matić-Kekić et al., 2007; Dedović et al., 2009, 2010). Program packages *Mathematica 5.0* (Wolfram Research, Inc., 2003) and *Statistica 8.0* (StatSoft, Inc., 2009) facilitated appliance of this method and those packages were successfully used in the papers related to agricultural problems (Matić-Kekić and Mudrinski, 2004, 2009; Matić-Kekić et al., 2008; Babić et al., 2011a and 2011b).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Under a closed household we imply a household with starting fund of inseminated heifers which in the next period doesn't obtain new heifers or buy new female or male calves, or sells the ones obtained with reproduction of livestock unit. In this paper we are going to derive mathematical formulae for a number of dairy cows in closed household. First, let us denote with p_1 percentage of calving, p_2 percentage of female offspring and p_3 percentage of twin offspring. Then, we can calculate an average annual percentage increase in number of female calves $\mathbf{p}$ by

$$(1) \quad \mathbf{p} = p_1 \cdot p_2 + p_1 \cdot p_2 \cdot p_3$$

For example, if percentage of calving is $p_1 = 80\%$, percentage of female offspring calving is $p_2 = 47\%$ and percentage of twin offspring calving is $p_3 = 3\%$, then average annual percentage increase in number of female calves is $\mathbf{p} = 38.73\%$. However, since 12% of female calves do not reach age of two (Etgen and Reaves, 1978), percentage of heifers in closed household after 2 years is equal to

$$(2) \quad \mathbf{p} = 0.88 \cdot \mathbf{p}.$$

CORRELATION BETWEEN PERCENTAGE INCREASES IN NUMBER OF COWS AND P_1 , P_2 AND P_3

Since UK is a region where cattle-breeding is extremely developed, we present the data from NUTS1 (Nomenclature for Units of Territorial Statistics level 1). Holstein influence appearing in 51% of all 3.47 million dairy cattle in the UK:

- Holstein Friesian (Friesian with more than 12.5% and less than 87.5% of Holstein blood): 1 765 000 (51%)
- Friesian (more than 87.5% Friesian blood): 1 079 000 (31%)
- Holstein (more than 87.5% of Holstein blood): 254 000 (7%)
- Holstein Friesian Cross (any of the above crossed with other breeds): 101 000 (3%)
- Other dairy breeds: 278 000 (8%).

In Serbia, Domestic Spotted cattle of Simmental type and Simmental cattle have an important place in cattle breeding (Bošnjak and Rodić, 2008). Out of the total number of cattle (1 153 000 head) about 40-50% falls into Simmental type, 30-40% into Domestic Spotted and about 20% into Black and white cattle and other breeds and crosses.

Analyzing data in Table 1, we can conclude that average annual percentage increase in number of female calves $\mathbf{p}$ is increased for about:

- 2.662% upon increase of calving for 5% (p_1);
- 2.637% upon decrease of female offspring calving for 3% (p_2);
- 0.863% upon increase of twin calving for 2% (p_3).

Therefore, the most influential parameter on average annual percentage of increasing the number of female calves $\mathbf{p}$ is the decrease of female offspring calves p_2 ($\mathbf{p} : p_2 = 1:1$), then the percentage of calving p_1 ($\mathbf{p} : p_1 = 0.5:1$) and finally, the percentage of twin calving p_3 ($\mathbf{p} : p_3 = 0.4:1$). Because of direct proportion between $\mathbf{p}$ and $\mathbf{p}$, influence of parameters p_1 , p_2 and p_3 is:

$$(3) \quad \mathbf{p} : p_2 = 0.88 : 1, \quad \mathbf{p} : p_1 = 0.44 : 1 \quad \text{and} \quad \mathbf{p} : p_3 = 0.352 : 1$$

However, large influence of twin calves should be taken examined carefully, because of widely known negative consequences of twin calving.

Table 1. Correlation between $\mathbf{p}$ and p_1, p_2, p_3 for different breeds of dairy cows

Tabela 1. Korelacija između $\mathbf{p}$ i p_1, p_2, p_3 za različite rase mlečnih krava

Breed Rasa	p_1	p_2	p_3	$\mathbf{p}$	$\mathbf{p}$
HF	0.8	0.47	0.03	0.3873	0.3408
S	0.8	0.5	0.05	0.42	0.3696
HxNCB HxR DŠ	0.8	0.5	0.03	0.412	0.3626
	0.85	0.5	0.03	0.4378	0.3852
	0.9	0.5	0.03	0.4635	0.4079
S	0.9	0.5	0.05	0.4725	0.4158
S	0.85	0.5	0.05	0.4463	0.3927
HF	0.9	0.47	0.03	0.4357	0.3834
HF	0.85	0.47	0.03	0.4115	0.3621
S	0.95	0.5	0.05	0.4988	0.4389

According to Čobić et al. (1995), genotype Simmental (S) (the total number of cows 710) has $p_2=49.83\%$, and genotypes Holstein x rotbunt (HxR) (the total number of cows 719) and Holstein x German black-white HxNCB) (the total number of cows 714) have $p_2=50.47\%$, while according to Nenadović et al. (1981) genotype Domestic spotted (DŠ) has $p_2=49.33\%$. Genotype Holstein-Friesian (HF) breed has $p_2= 46.7\%$. Average percentage of twin calving p_3 , is between 2.93% (Holstein-Friesian breed) to 4.97% (Simmental breed).

If veterinarian control is performed correctly during twin calving process of Simmental breed and if insemination of heifers is 90% successful, then Simmental breed is the leading breed by all parameters for main fund genotype selection, because of the largest increase of number of cows.

FORMULAE FOR THE NUMBER OF COWS

Let K be a number for inseminated heifers at the beginning (zero year) which will calve by the end of the year. With K_n we denote a number of dairy cows after n years, where at in that n year we don't count starting (zero) year. With $\mathbf{p}$ we denote an average annual percentage increase in number of female calves and all female calves are kept at the household and inseminated at the age of 14 -15 months, and then successfully calved at the age of 2 (there is $\mathbf{p}$ percentage of K). We have obtained recursive formula

$$(4) \quad K_n = K_{n-1} + p \cdot K_{n-2}.$$

For initial data $K_0 = K_1 = K$, using (4) we derive number of cows in the following years:

$$(5) \quad \begin{aligned} K_2 &= (1 + p) K = k_2 \cdot K \\ K_3 &= (1 + 2p) K = k_3 \cdot K \\ K_4 &= (1 + 3p + p^2) K = k_4 \cdot K \\ K_5 &= (1 + p)(1 + 3p) K = k_5 \cdot K \\ K_6 &= (1 + 5p + 6p^2 + p^3) K = k_6 \cdot K \end{aligned}$$

With k_n we have denoted the coefficient which multiply K in formulas for K_n , i.e. $k_1 = 1$, $k_2 = (1 + p)$, $k_3 = (1 + 2p)$, ... , $k_6 = (1 + 5p + 6p^2 + p^3)$. For average percentage increase in number of cows $p = 34.08\%$, which was derived with presumption that: percentage of calving $p_1 = 80\%$, percentage of female offspring $p_2 = 47\%$ and percentage of twin offspring $p_3 = 3\%$ values of coefficient k_n are calculated (Table 1, 2nd row) and graphically presented on Figure 1. In 3rd and 4th row of Table 2, there has been given the coefficients k_i , $i = 1, 2, \dots, 6$, which are stand for increase in number of dairy cows after i years, in comparison to starting number of inseminated cows K , for an average annual increase in number of cows $p = 40.79\%$ (when $p_1 = 90\%$, $p_2 = 47\%$ and $p_3 = 3\%$), i.e. $p = 43.89\%$ (when $p_1 = 95\%$, $p_2 = 50\%$ and $p_3 = 5\%$). Coefficients of cows by year k_i , $i = 1, 2, \dots, 9$ from 2nd, 3rd and 4th row of Table 2 are graphically presented on Figure 1. and marked with symbols $\blacklozenge$, $\square$ and $\blacktriangle$, respectively.

Table 2. Coefficient k_i , $i = 1, 2, \dots, 6$, average percentage increase in number of cows p in two years, and number of cows K_i , $i = 1, 2, \dots, 6$, in closed household at the end of the year i for initial number of inseminated heifers K

Tabela 2. Koeficijent k_i , $i = 1, 2, \dots, 6$ za prosečan procenat dvogodišnjeg uvećanja broja prvotelki p , i broj krava K_i , $i = 1, 2, \dots, 6$ u zatvorenom gazdinstvu na kraju i -te godine za početni broj osemenjenih junica K

p	k_1	k_2	k_3	k_4	k_5	k_6
0.3408	1	1.34	1.68	2.14	2.71	3.44
0.4079	1	1.41	1.82	2.4	3.13	4.11
0.4389	1	1.44	1.88	2.5	3.33	4.43
30	30	40	50	64	81	103
30	30	42	55	72	94	123
30	30	43	56	75	100	133
K	K_1	K_2	K_3	K_4	K_5	K_6

In 5th, 6th and 7th row of Table 2, if the starting number of inseminated cows is $K=30$, then number of dairy cows is K_i , $i=1, 2, \dots, 6$ in closed household at the end of year i , consecutive for average percentage increase in number of cows after two years $p = 34.08\%$, (5th row), $p = 40,79\%$ (6th row), i.e. $p = 43,89\%$ (7th row).

Graph. 1. Graph of coefficients values of increasing number of cows k_i , $i=1,2,\dots,9$ for average percentage increase in number of cows (34.08%, 40.79% and 43.89%)

Grafikon 1. Prikaz vrednosti koeficijenta uvećanja broja muznih krava k_i , $i = 1, 2, \dots, 9$ za prosečan procenat dvogodišnjeg uvećanja broja prvotelki p (34,08%, 40,79% i 43,89%).

Using the formula (2), we have calculated percentage p (Table 3, 1st column) which depends on p , p_1 , p_2 and p_3 (Table 3, last three columns). Now, using the recursive formula (4) we have calculated coefficients k_i at year i , $i=1,2,\dots,9$ (Table 3, columns 2-9).

Table 3. Coefficients k_i for $i = 1, 2, \dots, 9$, for different percentage of calving p_p calving of female calves percentage p_2 , and twin calving percentage p_3 .

Tabela 3. Koeficijenti godišnjeg uvećanja broja muznih krava k_i , $i = 1, 2, \dots, 9$ za razne vrednosti procenta teljenja p_p procenta teljenja ženskih teladi p_2 i procenta teljenja blizanaca p_3 .

p	k_1	k_2	k_3	k_4	k_5	k_6	k_7	k_8	k_9	p_1	p_2	p_3
0.3626	1	1.36	1.73	2.22	2.84	3.65	4.68	6	7.7	0.8	0.5	0.03
0.3347	1	1.33	1.67	2.12	2.68	3.39	4.28	5.41	6.84	0.8	0.47	0.05
0.3834	1	1.38	1.77	2.3	2.98	3.86	5	6.47	8.39	0.9	0.47	0.03
0.3909	1	1.39	1.78	2.33	3.02	3.94	5.11	6.65	8.65	0.9	0.47	0.05
0.4158	1	1.42	1.83	2.42	3.18	4.19	5.51	7.25	9.54	0.9	0.5	0.05
0.3927	1	1.39	1.78	2.33	3.03	3.95	5.14	6.69	8.71	0.85	0.5	0.05
0.3852	1	1.38	1.77	2.30	2.99	3.87	5.02	6.52	8.45	0.85	0.5	0.03
0.3621	1	1.36	1.72	2.22	2.84	3.64	4.67	5.99	7.69	0.85	0.47	0.03

Using program package *Statistica 8.0*, it has been determined a strong correlation between k_i at year i of calving ($R^2=99.86\%$). Exponential dependence has been derived and created a mathematical model in order to derive the coefficients c_1 and c_2 using least square method

$$(6) \quad k_i = c_1 \cdot \text{Exp}(c_2 \cdot i) \text{ for } i = 1, 2, \dots, 9$$

for typical coefficient values of k_i in Table 3, with $p=41.58\%$. Function in (6) is shown in Graph 2.

As it was shown (Matić-Kekić 2006b), program package Excel is unreliable since the parameter c_1 does not belong to its 95% confidence interval calculated using the program package *Statistica 8.0*. So we relied on program package *Statistica 8.0*.

Graph 2. Correlation between coefficients k_i and year i of calving – mathematical model at the program package *Statistica 8.0* (left) and the program package *Excel* (right)
*Grafikon 2. Korelacija između koeficijenata k_i i godine i teljenja – matematički model rađen u programima *Statistika 8.0* (levo) i *Excel* (desno)*

CONCLUSIONS

We have derived the formula $(2) \mathbf{p} = 0.88 \cdot \mathbf{p} = 0.88 \cdot (p_1 \cdot p_2 + p_1 \cdot p_2 \cdot p_3)$, where $\mathbf{p}$ stands for average percentage increase in number of cows after two years, $\mathbf{p}$ stands for average annual percentage increase in number of female calves an initial number of inseminated heifers K , p_1 average percentages of calving, p_2 calving of female calves percentage and p_3 twin calving percentage. Simmental breed is leading breed by all parameters ($\mathbf{p}$, $\mathbf{p}$, p_2 and p_3) for main fund genotype selection because of the largest increase of number of cows. The most influential parameter on $\mathbf{p}$ is the decrease of percentage of female offspring calves p_2 . Parameters p_1 , p_2 and p_3 influence on percentage of new cows is: $\mathbf{p} : p_2 = 0.88 : 1$, $\mathbf{p} : p_1 = 0.44 : 1$ and $\mathbf{p} : p_3 = 0.352 : 1$. It has been derived formula $(4) K_n = K_{n-1} + \mathbf{p} \cdot K_{n-2}$ with initial data $K_0 = K_1 = K$ for number of dairy cows K_n at the end of year n at closed household. K_n depends on K and $\mathbf{p}$, where K represents the number of successfully inseminated heifers in the zero year, which we can expect their cows until zero year is finished. It has been calculated the coefficients k_i of cows number increase per year i and number of cows K_i , for $i=1,2,\dots,6$ for initial fund $K=30$ inseminated heifers for average percentage increase in number of cows after two years $\mathbf{p}=34.08\%$ (with $p_1 = 80\%$, $p_2 = 47\%$ and $p_3 = 3\%$ for Holstein-Friesian breed), $\mathbf{p} = 40.79\%$ (with $p_1 = 90\%$, $p_2 = 50\%$ and $p_3 = 3\%$ for Domestic spotted and Holstein breeds) and $\mathbf{p} = 43.89\%$ (with $p_1 = 95\%$, $p_2 = 50\%$ and $p_3 = 5\%$ for Simmental breed) in Table 1, and Figure 1. Changing the percentage of calving p_1 , we have obtained coefficients k_i , which are presented in Table 2.

The proposed formulae can be used for numerous additional financial analyses in milk production. For example, if the grace period for the term of the credit repayment of

5 years, it is easy to determine what starting fund K is required in order to have a dairy cattle fund of 50 cows after 5 years.

Since $k_4=2.51$ (Table 2, 4th row), it means that initial fund must contain 20 inseminated calves of Simmental breed. In case of Dutch-Friesian, if the percentage of calving is 80%, then initial fund must contain 24 inseminated calves.

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REKURZIVNA FORMULA ZA BROJ KRAVA U OKVIRU PROIZVODNJE MLEKA

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Izvod

Neka je početni broj osemenjenih junica označen sa K , dok su sa p_1 , p_2 i p_3 označeni redom prosečni procenti teljenja, teljenja ženskog teleta i teljenja blizanaca. Uz fiksiranje vremena uspešnog osemenjavanja na 14-15 meseci starosti junica izvedena je formula za maksimalan broj mlečnih krava K_n u proizvodnji mleka na zatvorenom gazdinstvu, dobijen od polaznog fonda od K steonih junica, nakon n godina. Na primer, za $n = 4$ je

$$K_4 = (1 + p) \cdot (1 + 3p) \cdot K,$$

gde je p 88% od p , a sa p je označen godišnji prosečni procenat uvećanja broja ženske teladi $p = p_1 \cdot p_2 + p_1 \cdot p_2 \cdot p_3$. Izvršena je analiza za koliko procenata se povećava broj grla u proizvodnji mleka K_n , ako procenat teljenja varira od 80% do 90%, za $n = 2, 3, 4, 5, 6$. Predložene formule mogu da posluže za mnogobrojne dodatne finansijske analize u proizvodnji mleka. Tako, na primer, ako je "grace" period za otplatu kredita 5 godina, lako može da se utvrdi koliki početni fond K je potrebno zasnovati pa da se nakon 5 godina ima muzni fond od 50 grla.

Ključne reči: zatvoreno gazdinstvo, model uvećanja stada, finansijska analiza, proizvodnja mleka, steone junice.

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